

Press Release

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NERO, the Advanced Cybersecurity awareness ecosystem for SMEs

The new European Support Action project gathers a set of frameworks to protect small business – in healthcare, finance, and transport – from cyber threats.

[January 2024] NERO is a new EU-funded, 36-month project that supports the European adoption of innovative and up-to-date cybersecurity solutions to prepare, protect and respond to cyber threats across Europe.

Coordinated by **trustilio** (<https://trustilio.com/>), the NERO project kicked off in December 2023 in Athens, Greece, with a consortium of 16 partners convening at the University of Piraeus.

In essence, NERO combines cybersecurity skill enhancement and tools to elevate capacities and capabilities, especially for SMEs and public organisations. Its **advanced Cybersecurity Ecosystem** (made of tools and use cases) comprises **five interrelated frameworks** (VICTORIOUS, ARCANA, AUDACIOUS, CYBIT, and ASTRAS), designed to deliver a comprehensive Cybersecurity Awareness program. Following ENISA's recommendations, this approach is the best way to educate and cultivate a security-first culture, guiding employees on mitigating the impact of cyber threats through activities, resources, and training.

The efficacy of these frameworks will be validated through three **use case demonstrations** in different domains, allowing the tools to operate in real conditions:

1. Enhancing Patient Data Security in **Healthcare** through Cybersecurity Tools;
2. Strengthening Supply Chain Resilience through Cybersecurity Awareness in the **transportation** and **Logistics** Industry;
3. Boosting **Financial Security** through Enhanced Cybersecurity Awareness and Tools.

The project will roll out around **three phases**: first, the analysis of the current cybersecurity landscape. Second, the creation of a Marketplace of existing tools, to provide SMEs with a Cyber Immunity Toolkit Repository. Third, a Cyber Resilience Program and Cyber Awareness Training with a gamification approach, accessible through the Marketplace.

SMEs interested in participating in the training can express their interest by visiting: <https://nerocybersecurity.eu/reach-out-us>.

NERO marks a shift of focus from research and development to supporting the market uptake and exposure of innovative cybersecurity solutions and improving knowledge and auditing of the cybersecurity preparedness of SMEs.

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